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Research Article

Development And Validation Of An RP-UPLC Method For The Determination Of Memantine And Donepezil In Capsule Dosage Form, Including A Comprehensive Stability Study

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ABSTRACT

RP-UPLC developed a simple, accurate and precise method for the simultaneous estimation of memantine and donepezil in capsule. The chromatogram was run through an ACQUITY UPLC CSH C18 column, 1.7 μ m, 2.1 mm x 50 mm. A mobile phase containing 0.01 N KH₂PO₄ buffer and 60:40 methanol was pumped through the column at a flow rate of 0.4 ml/min. The temperature was maintained at 38.0 °C. The optimized wavelength for memantine and donepezil was 250 nm. The retention times of memantine and donepezil were 0.572 minutes and 1.367 minutes, respectively. The percent RSD for memantine and donepezil were 0.4 and 0.6, respectively. The recovery rate was 100.43% and 99.95% for memantine and donepezil. The LOD and LOQ values obtained from the regression equations for memantine and donepezil were 0.13 ppm, 0.41 ppm and 0.09 ppm, 0.26 ppm, respectively. The regression equation for memantine is $y = 8913.2x + 10674$ and for donepezil $y = 8018.2x + 4057.2$. The storage times are shortened and the working time is shortened.

INTRODUCTION

The German psychiatrist and neuropathologist Dr. Alois Alzheimer is credited with describing for the first time a dementing condition which later became known as AD. In his landmark 1906 conference lecture and a subsequent 1907 article, Alzheimer described the case of Auguste D, a 51-year-old woman with a ‘peculiar disease of the

cerebral cortex,’ who had presented with progressive memory and language impairment, disorientation, behavioral symptoms (hallucinations, delusions, paranoia), and psychosocial impairment.¹³ Remarkably, many of the clinical observations and pathological findings that Alzheimer described more than a century ago

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continue to remain central to our understanding of AD today. There is no cure for AD, and drug therapy for the disease is still in its infancy. Approved medications for the treatment of probable AD help control the symptoms of AD but do not slow down the progression or reverse the course of the disease itself. At present, the mainstay of AD therapy are drugs that target neurotransmitter systems in the brain. AD primarily damages glutamate and acetylcholine-producing neurons and their associated synapses, and this damage correlates well with early cognitive symptoms of AD. Acetylcholinesterase inhibitors help improve memory function and attention in AD patients by interfering with the breakdown of acetylcholine, thereby increasing the levels of the neurotransmitter at the synapse. There are currently three FDA-approved cholinesterase inhibitors: rivastigmine and galantamine (for mild to moderate AD), and donepezil (for all stages of AD). Memantine is another FDA-approved medication for use in moderate to severe AD but belongs to a different class of drugs known as NMDA (glutamate) receptor antagonists. Both classes of medications are generally well-tolerated, with gastrointestinal upset, dizziness, and headache being the most common adverse effects observed. UPLC's high sensitivity is beneficial for detecting trace levels of donepezil and memantine in biological samples, providing valuable insights into drug metabolism and distribution. It allows for the simultaneous detection of multiple compounds. This is particularly relevant when studying drug combinations, as it enables researchers to monitor the presence and concentrations of both donepezil and memantine in a single analysis. This is important in clinical research where timely results are essential for treatment adjustments and decision-making. While the initial investment in UPLC technology may be higher, the operational costs can be lower due to reduced solvent

consumption and shorter analysis times. UPLC systems typically require smaller sample volumes, which can be crucial when working with limited or precious samples. UPLC systems often exhibit higher peak capacity, allowing for the analysis of more compounds in a single run. Hence the current work serves to be first to elucidate the systematic implementation and to the development of simple, accurate and robust validated RP-UPLC method.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Memantine and Donepezil pure drugs (API), Combination Donepezil and Memantine Capsules (Namzaric), Distilled water, Acetonitrile, Phosphate buffer, Methanol, Potassium dihydrogen ortho phosphate buffer, Orthophosphoric acid. All the above chemicals and solvents are from Rankem.

Instruments:

Electronics Balance-Denver, pH meter -BVK enterprises, India, Ultrasonicator-BVK enterprises, UPLC instrument used was of WATERS UPLC SYSTEM with Auto Injector and Acquity TUV detector. Software used is Empower 2, UV-VIS spectrophotometer PG Instruments T60 with special bandwidth of 2 mm and 10mm and matched quartz cells integrated with UV win 6 Software was used for measuring absorbances of Memantine and Donepezil solutions.

Methods:

Diluent:

Based up on the solubility of the drugs, diluent was selected methanol and Water taken in the ratio of 60:40.

Preparation of buffer:

0.01N K_2HPO_4 Buffer: Accurately weighed 1.38gm of Potassium phosphate in a 1000ml of Volumetric flask add about 900ml of milli-Q water added and degas to sonicate and finally make up the volume with water then PH adjusted to 4.8 with dil. OPA.

Buffer: (0.1% Ortho phosphoric acid)

1ML of Ortho phosphoric acid solution in a 1000ml of volumetric flask add about 100ml of milli-Q water and final volume make up to 1000 ml with milli-Q water.

Preparation of Standard stock solutions:

Accurately weighed 14 mg of Memantine, 10mg of Donepezil and transferred to 50ml volumetric flask and 3/4 th of diluents was added to these flasks and sonicated for 10 minutes. Flask was made up with diluents and labeled as Standard stock solution. (280µg/ml of Memantine and 200µg/ml of Donepezil)

Preparation of Standard working solutions (100% solution):

1ml from stock solution was pipetted out and taken into a 10ml volumetric flask and made up with diluent. (28µg/ml Memantine of and 20µg/ml of Donepezil)

Preparation of Sample stock solutions:

10 Capsules were weighed and the average weight of each Capsule was calculated, then the weight equivalent to one Capsule(14mg/10mg) was transferred into a 100 ml volumetric flask, 5ml of diluents was added and sonicated for 25 min, further the volume was made up with diluent and filtered by HPLC filters (140µg/ml of Memantine and 100µg/ml of Donepezil)

Preparation of Sample working solutions (100% solution):

2ml of filtered sample stock solution was transferred to 10ml volumetric flask and made up with diluent. (28µg/ml of Memantine and 20µg/ml of Donepezil)

Validation:

System suitability parameters:

The system suitability parameters were determined by preparing standard solutions of Memantine (28ppm) and Donepezil 20ppm) and the solutions were injected six times and the parameters like peak tailing, resolution and USP plate count were determined.

The % RSD for the area of six standard injections results should not be more than 2%.

Specificity:

Checking of the interference in the optimized method. We should not find interfering peaks in blank and placebo at retention times of these drugs in this method. So this method was said to be specific.

Precision:

Preparation of Sample stock solutions:

10 Capsules were weighed and the average weight of each Capsule was calculated, then the weight equivalent to one Capsule(14mg/10mg) was transferred into a 100 ml volumetric flask, 5ml of diluents was added and sonicated for 25 min, further the volume was made up with diluent and filtered by HPLC filters (140µg/ml of Memantine and 100µg/ml of Donepezil).

Preparation of Sample working solutions (100% solution):

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The Precision were determined by preparing Sample solutions of Memantine (28ppm) and Donepezil 20ppm) and the solutions were injected six times and the % RSD for the area of six standard injections results should not be more than 2%.

Linearity:

• **Preparation of Standard stock solutions:**

Accurately weighed 14 mg of Memantine, 10mg of Donepezil and transferred to 50ml volumetric flask and 3/4 th of diluents was added to these flasks and sonicated for 10 minutes. Flask was made up with diluents and labeled as Standard stock solution. (280µg/ml of Memantine and 200µg/ml of Donepezil)

- After the preparation of standard stock solution using stock solution preparation of 25% to 150% (0.25ml ,

0.5ml,0.75ml,1ml,1.25ml,1.5ml.) standard solution was prepared.

Accuracy:

Preparation of Sample stock solutions:

10 Capsules were weighed and the average weight of each Capsule was calculated, then the weight equivalent to one Capsule(14mg/10mg) was transferred into a 100 ml volumetric flask, 5ml of diluents was added and sonicated for 25 min, further the volume was made up with diluent and filtered by HPLC filters (140µg/ml of Memantine and 100µg/ml of Donepezil).

Preparation of Standard working solutions (100% solution):

1ml from stock solution was pipetted out and taken into a 10ml volumetric flask and made up with diluent. (28µg/ml Memantine of and 20µg/ml of Donepezil)

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1ml from stock solution was pipetted out and taken into a 10ml volumetric flask and made up with diluent. (14µg/ml Memantine of and 10µg/ml of Donepezil)

Preparation of 50% Spiked Solution:

0.5ml of sample stock solution was taken into a 10ml volumetric flask, to that 1.0ml from each standard stock solution was pipetted out, and made up to the mark with diluent.

Preparation of 100% Spiked Solution:

1.0ml of sample stock solution was taken into a 10ml volumetric flask, to that 1.0ml from each standard stock solution was pipetted out, and made up to the mark with diluent.

Preparation of 150% Spiked Solution: 1.5ml of sample stock solution was taken into a 10ml volumetric flask, to that 1.0ml from each standard stock solution was pipetted out, and made up to the mark with diluent.

Acceptance Criteria:

The % Recovery for each level should be between 98.0 to 102

Robustness:

- Small deliberate changes in method like Flow rate, mobile phase ratio, and temperature are made but there was no recognized change in the result and are within range as per ICH Guide lines.
- Robustness conditions like Flow minus (0.3ml/min), Flow plus (0.5ml/min), mobile phase minus, mobile phase plus, temperature minus (25°C) and temperature plus(35°C) was maintained and samples were injected in duplicate manner. System suitability parameters were not much effected and all the parameters were passed. %RSD was within the limit.

LOD sample Preparation:

0.25ml each from two standard stock solutions was pipetted out and transferred to two separate 10ml volumetric flasks and made up with diluents. From the above solutions 0.3ml each of Memantine, Donepezil solutions respectively were transferred to 10ml volumetric flasks and made up with the same diluents

LOQ sample Preparation:

0.25ml each from two standard stock solutions was pipetted out and transferred to two separate 10ml volumetric flask and made up with diluent. From the above solutions 0.9ml each of Memantine, Donepezil solutions respectively were transferred to 10ml volumetric flasks and made up with the same diluent.

Degradation studies:

Oxidation:

To 1 ml of stock solution of Memantine and Donepezil, 1 ml of 20% hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) was added separately. The solutions were kept for 30 min at 60°C. For HPLC study, the resultant solution was diluted to obtain 28µg/ml & 20µg/ml solution and 10 µl were injected into the system and the chromatograms were recorded to assess the stability of sample.

Acid Degradation Studies:

To 1 ml of stock solution Memantine and Donepezil, 1ml of 2N Hydrochloric acid was added and refluxed for 30mins at 600 C. The resultant solution was diluted to obtain 28µg/ml & 20µg/ml solution and 10 µl solutions were injected into the system and the chromatograms were recorded to assess the stability of sample.

Alkali Degradation Studies:

To 1 ml of stock solution Memantine and Donepezil, 1 ml of 2N sodium hydroxide was added and refluxed for 30mins at 600c. The resultant solution was diluted to obtain 28µg/ml & 20µg/ml solution and 10 µl were injected into the system and the chromatograms were recorded to assess the stability of sample.

Dry Heat Degradation Studies:

The standard drug solution was placed in oven at 105°C for 1 h to study dry heat degradation. For HPLC study, the resultant solution was diluted to 28µg/ml & 20µg/ml solution and 10µl were injected into the system and the chromatograms were recorded to assess the stability of the sample.

Photo Stability Studies:

The photochemical stability of the drug was also studied by exposing the 280µg/ml & 200µg/ml solution to UV Light by keeping the beaker in UV Chamber for 1days or 200 Watt hours/m² in photo stability chamber. For HPLC study, the resultant solution was diluted to obtain 28µg/ml & 20µg/ml solutions and 10 µl were injected into the system and the chromatograms were recorded to assess the stability of sample.

Neutral Degradation Studies:

Stress testing under neutral conditions was studied by refluxing the drug in water for 1hrs at a temperature of 60°. For HPLC study, the resultant solution was diluted to 28µg/ml & 20µg/ml solution and 10 µl were injected into the system and the chromatograms were recorded to assess the stability of the sample.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

System suitability:

All the system suitability parameters are within range and satisfactory as per ICH guidelines.

Table: 1 System suitability studies of Donepezil and Memantine method

Property	Donepezil	Memantine
Retention time (t _R)	0.572± 0.3 min	1.367±0.3min
Theoretical plates (N)	4586± 163.48	7123± 163.48
Tailing factor (T)	1.04 ± 0.117	1.12± 0.117

Sr. no.	Memantine			Donepezil				
	Injection	RT(min)	USP Plate Count	Tailing	RT(min)	USP Plate Count	Tailing	Resolution
1		0.534	4518	1.06	1.364	7144	1.03	14.8
2		0.535	4575	1.04	1.365	7185	1.04	14.9
3		0.535	4529	1.08	1.365	7042	1.02	14.8
4		0.535	4524	1.07	1.365	7174	1.01	14.9
5		0.536	4541	1.07	1.366	7096	1.04	14.9
6		0.536	4523	1.04	1.371	7059	1.04	14.9

Specificity-

Fig : 1 Chromatogram of blank.

Fig:2 Typical chromatogram of Donepezil and Memantine.

Linearity:

6 Linear concentrations of Donepezil (5ppm-30ppm) and Memantine (7ppm to 42 ppm) are prepared and injected. Regression equation of the

the Donepezil and Memantine are found to be, $y = 8018.2x + 4057.2$ and $y = 8913.2x + 10674$. and the regression co-efficient was 0.999.

Table: 2 Calibration data of Donepezil and Memantine method.

S.no	Concentration Donepezil (µg/ml)	Response	Concentration Memantine (µg/ml)	Response
1	0	0	0	0
2	5	44825	7	73385
3	10	85831	14	137034
4	15	119470	21	196569
5	20	166035	28	257508
6	25	206110	35	324051
7	30	243980	42	385731

Fig: 3 Calibration curve of Donepezil

Fig: 4 Calibration curve of Memantine

Precision: Donepezil and Memantine were found to be 1.0% and 0.4% respectively.
 Intraday precision (Repeatability): Intraday precision was performed and % RSD for

Table: 3 Repeatability results for Donepezil and Memantine.

Sr. No.	Donepezil	Memantine
1	166110	265949
2	169428	265018
3	167020	267349
4	167425	266419
5	168089	263657
6	167098	263511
Mean	167528	265317
Std. Dev.	1130.4	1539.4
%RSD	0.7	0.6

Intraday precision (Method Precision):

Inter day precision was performed with 10 hrs time lag and the %RSD Obtained for Donepezil and Memantine were 0.4% and 0.5%.

Table 4 Method precision results for Donepezil and Memantine.

Sr. No.	Memantine	Donepezil
1	260008	168050
2	261644	169882
3	260927	169865
4	260011	168294
5	262109	169404
6	262376	168015
Mean	261179	168918
Std. Dev.	1030.8	896.7
%RSD	0.4	0.5

Inter-day precision (Intermediate Precision):

Inter day precision was performed with 10 hrs time lag and the %RSD Obtained for Donepezil and Memantine were 0.6% and 0.4%.

Table 5 Intermediate precision results for Donepezil and Memantine.

Sr. No.	Memantine	Donepezil
1	259445	162880
2	259626	161206
3	260935	163203
4	261429	161738
5	259041	161662
6	258626	163365
Mean	259850	162342
Std. Dev.	1099	916.0
%RSD	0.4	0.6

Accuracy:

Three concentrations 50%, 100%, 150%, were injected in a triplicate manner and amount

Recovered and % Recovery were displayed in Table 6.5 & 6.6.

Table: 6 Accuracy results of Memantine

% Level	Amount Spiked (µg/mL)	Amount recovered (µg/mL)	% Recovery	Mean %Recovery
50%	14	14.03	100.21	100.43%
	14	14.12	100.83	
	14	14.06	100.40	
100%	28	28.07	100.24	
	28	28.24	100.85	
	28	28.25	100.89	
150	42	42.25	100.60	
	42	42.05	100.11	
	42	41.90	99.77	

Table: 7 Accuracy results of Donepezil

% Level	Amount Spiked (µg/mL)	Amount recovered (µg/mL)	% Recovery	Mean %Recovery
50%	10	9.98	99.80	99.95%
	10	9.98	99.76	
	10	10.06	100.61	
100%	20	20.04	100.21	
	20	19.99	99.95	
	20	19.91	99.57	
150	30	29.72	99.07	
	30	29.99	99.95	
	30	30.20	100.66	

LOD:

LOD for Donepezil was found to be 0.09 and Memantine was 0.13 respectively.

2LOQ:

LOQ for Donepezil and Memantine were found to be 0.41 and 0.26 respective

Assay:

Standard preparations are made from the API and Sample Preparations are from Formulation. Both sample and standards are injected six homogeneous samples. Drug in the formulation was estimated by taking the standard as the reference. The Average % Assay was calculated and found to be 99.29% and 99.99% for Donepezil and Memantine respectively.

Preparation of Sample stock solutions:

10 Capsules were weighed and the average weight of each Capsule was calculated, then the weight equivalent to one Capsule was transferred into a 100 ml volumetric flask, 5ml of diluents was added and sonicated for 25 min, further the volume was made up with diluent and filtered by HPLC filters (140µg/ml of Memantine and 100µg/ml of Donepezil)

Preparation of Sample working solutions (100% solution):

2ml of filtered sample stock solution was transferred to 10ml volumetric flask and made up with diluent. (14µg/ml of Memantine and 10µg/ml of Donepezil)

$$\% \text{ Assay} = \frac{\text{AT} \times \text{WS} \times 100 \times \text{P} \times \text{AV}}{\text{AS} \times 50 \times 10 \times 1 \times 2 \times 100 \times \text{L.C}} \times 100$$

AT	Average Peak area of Test solution
AS	Mean peak area of standard solution
WS	Weight of working standard taken in mg
P	Assay of working standard in % on dried basis
L.C	Label Claim
AV	AVG wt of Capsule

Table 8 Assay Chromatogram Table:

S. No.	Donepezil %Assay	Memantine %Assay
1	99.47	99.61
2	100.55	100.24
3	100.54	99.96
4	99.61	99.61
5	100.27	100.42
6	99.44	100.52
AVG	99.98	100.06
STDEV	0.5307	0.39
%RSD	0.5	0.4

Fig No.4. Standard Assay Chromatogram Donepezil and Memantine

Fig 5 Working Sample Assay Chromatogram Donepezil and Memantine

Degradation data

Type of degradation	Donepezil		Memantine	
	%RECOVERED	% DEGRADED	%RECOVERED	% DEGRADED
Acid	93.11	6.89	93.69	6.31
Base	94.27	5.73	94.18	5.82
Peroxide	95.18	4.82	94.80	5.20
Thermal	99.08	0.92	99.01	0.99
Uv	98.34	1.66	99.00	1.00
Water	99.25	0.75	99.56	0.44

Degradation chromatograms

Acid degradation chromatogram

Fig.6 acid

Base degradation chromatogram

Fig 7 base

Peroxide degradation chromatogram

Fig. 8 peroxide

Thermal degradation chromatogram

Fig. 9. Thermal

Uv degradation chromatogram

Fig. 10 UV

Water degradation chromatogram

Fig. 11 water

CONCLUSION:

A simple, Accurate, precise method was developed for the simultaneous estimation of the

Donepezil and Memantine in Capsule dosage form. Retention time of Memantine and Donepezil were found to be 0.572 min and 1.367 min. %RSD

of the Memantine and Donepezil were and found to be 0.4 and 0.6 respectively. %Recover was Obtained as 100.43% and 99.95% for Memantine and Donepezil. LOD, LOQ values were obtained from regression equations of Memantine and Donepezil were 0.13ppm, 0.41ppm and 0.09ppm, 0.26ppm respectively. Regression equation of Memantine is $y = 8913.2x + 10674$, and of Donepezil is $y = 8018.2x + 4057.2$, Retention times are decreased and that run time was decreased so the method developed was simple and economical that can be adopted in regular.

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